

REVIEW PAPER

THE CONJUGAL RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF PARTIES TO A STATUTORY MARRIAGE IN NIGERIA

Ajabor, Ifeanyi¹ and Stephen C. Chukwuma²

¹Directorate of General Studies, Delta State Polytechnic, Ozoro, Delta State Nigeria.

²Department of Arts and Humanities, School of General Studies, Delta-State Polytechnic, Ogwashi-Uku Delta-State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

In every community in Nigeria today, the issue of marriage attracts great attention. This is because of the value the society placed on the institution of marriage. Be that as it may, it is sad to note that dissolution of marriage is as-popular as marriage itself, with its attendant side effects, on the children, husband, wife and the society at large. It is therefore imperative that couples going into marriage relationship should not only understand the meaning of marriage but also to be abreast with their rights and obligations arising thereof. The fulcrum of this paper is to evaluate the reciprocal rights and obligations of parties in marriage contracted under the statutory law. The paper concludes by making recommendations with a view to solving many marital problems

KEYWORDS: Conjugal Rights, Obligations, Community, Marriage, Parties, Relationship

Received for Publication: 22/06/15

Accepted for Publication: 18/10/15

Corresponding Author: ifyajabor12@uamail.com

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is a universal institution which is recognized and respected all over the world. It is safe to say that it is becoming almost compulsory for every adult in our contemporary society to get married irrespective of one's status in life. As a social institution, marriage is founded on and governed by the social and religious norms of society, consequently, the sanctity of marriage is a well-accepted principle in the world community. Marriage is the root of the family. It is a generally accepted norm in Nigeria that marriage, being a union of man and woman, involves two persons of the opposite sex. It means that sex constitute an essential determination of marriage relations. In other words, to establish the existence of a valid marriage, it must be proving that the persons involved are man and woman. However, this issue has been complicated by the existence of hermaphrodites and advanced Medical Science that has made sex change operation feasible. A legal question has to be asked at this Juncture, whether such marriage between such person can be said to be legal. It was held to be invalid in the case of **Corbett V Corbett**, In this case the Court held that a male who has undergone a sex change operation was physically incapable of consummating a marriage and that using the artificial cavity could never constitute a true intercourse. It has to be between a man and a woman. There have to be some conditions which must be met to make a marriage legal.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

Objective

The objective of this study is to evaluate the reciprocal rights and obligations of parties in marriage contracted under the statutory law in Nigeria.

Definition of Marriage

Marriage by universal definition is the legal relationship between husband and wife. It is a union between a man and a woman, at least so we thought until recently. According to Marrian Webster's Collegiate Dictionary (2003), marriage is defined as a state of being united to a person of the opposite sex as husband or wife, in a consensual and contractual relationship recognized by law.

According to Black Law- Dictionary (2004), marriage is a legal union of couple as husband and wife. Lord Penzance defines it in the case of **Hyde V Hyde** as a voluntary union for life, of one man and woman to the exclusion of all others.

Three aspects of this definition are of prime importance; first, it must be a voluntary union. Secondly, the union must be for life. The cardinal requirement here is that at the time of contracting it, the parties intended that it should be for life unless dissolved by a Court of competent jurisdiction via a process proscribed by law. Thirdly, it must be a union of one man and one woman to the exclusion of all others. This requirement distinguished

monogamous system of marriage from polygamous one

Types of Marriage

There are two types of marriage in Nigeria viz: Customary Law Marriage and Marriage under the Act. Before Nigeria became a British colony, only customary marriage was carried out. This included Islamic marriage.

Customary Law Marriage/Islamic Law Marriage.

This is a system of marriage where by one man is married to more than one woman. This is a system of marriage that has no limit of numbers of wives a man can marry within his life time. However, Islamic law requires that the maximum number of wives a man can marry is four. This system of marriage still subsists in Nigeria.

However, the present economic hardship and the change of occupation from farming to other fields of economic undertakings have pushed many Nigerians from the love of many wives and consequential large number of children to marriage under the Act.

Generally, the followings are the prerequisites for a valid customary law marriage.

1. **Betrothal:** This is simply an agreement to marry. The two parties agree to marry and their parents or families take over. They make discreet investigation of each other's families with a view to deciding if their children should marry into the other family. This process is carried out by intermediaries and if positive both parties gear up for further ceremonies. Since betrothal is just a mere promise to marry, a breach of the promise to marry is not actionable under customary law.
2. **Consent:** The intending couples have to give their consent to a customary marriage. The Supreme Court in the case of **Osanwonyi V Osanwonyi** held that under Bini Native law and custom the consent of the parties was necessary for a valid marriage under customary law.

Furthermore, under the Criminal Code Act 6, it is an offence punishable with seven years imprisonment for any person who with the intent to marry a female person of any age or cause her to be married by any other person, takes her away or detain her against her will. Furthermore, parental consent is necessary before a valid customary marriage can take place. In **Okpanum V Okpanum** the High Court of East central state of Nigeria

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

held that in order to constitute a valid customary law marriage, there must be parental consent and mutual agreement between the parties.

3. **Capacity:** This relates to the age of the couples. There is no doubt that before the year 2003, there was no law against child marriage most of which occur in the Northern parts of the country. Since the passing of the child's Rights Act, no marriage of person below the age of eighteen years is allowed under Nigerian Law.
4. **Marriage Consideration otherwise called Dowry or Bride Price.** This is one of the essential requirements of a valid customary marriage. By whatever name called, the bride price includes any gift or payment in the form of money, natural produce or any kind of property given by an intending husband and his family to the parents or guardian of a female person on account of the marriage. Payment of bride price is an important element of customary law marriage.
5. **Solemnization:** This generally involves breaking kola, pouring libation, sharing drinks and other activities. The bride is invariably handed over to the bridegroom and his family. In **Omoga V Bedego** the Court held that there must be a formal handing over of the bride to the groom in the presence of the two families and witnesses and the acceptance and taking away of the bride to her husband's house under Yoruba Native Law and custom to be valid.
6. **Consummation of the Marriage:** Consummation simply means having sex with a view to making a marriage complete. In traditional societies, the very night of the marriage is eagerly awaited by the groom's family as he is expected to announce his exploits to his family and state if his wife was found intact or not.

Marriage under the Act

This is also regarded as the monogamous system of marriage. In other words; it is a marriage between one man and one woman. This system of marriage is regulated by the Marriage Act and the Matrimonial Causes Act respectively.

In statutory marriage, the contractual aspects are fully developed along the line of English Law of contract.

Essential Elements of a Valid Statutory Marriage

Under the Marriage Act, the conditions for a valid marriage are articulated although there are some lacunas in some areas.

1. **Age:** The Marriage Act does not lay down any mandatory age for marriage: This vacuum on important and fundamental matter is a serious omission which requires immediate remedial action. Section 3 (1) (e) of the Matrimonial Cause Act, 1970 makes marriage void where either of the parties is not of "marriageable age". But nowhere in the statute is the term "marriageable age" defined. However, the child's rights Act passed into law in 2003 specifically prohibit the marriage of a person under eighteen years whether male or female. The relevant provision reads as follows "no person under the age of eighteen is capable of contracting a valid marriage and accordingly a marriage so contracted is null and void and of now effect whatsoever" Furthermore betrothal of a person under 18 years is completely forbidden.
2. **Prohibited Degrees of Consanguinity and Affinity:** Marriage under the Act does not accept couples who have blood relationship to get married. It is a good ground for breaking the marriage under the Act. Under the statute, a marriage is prohibited if the woman is or has been the man's ancestress, descendant, sister, father's sister, mother's sister, sister brother's daughter, sister's daughter. Marriage is also prohibited on the ground of affinity between a man and his wife's mother, wife's grandmother, wife's daughter, wife's son's daughter, wife's daughter's daughter, father's wife, ground father's wife, son's wife, son's son wife, daughter's son's wife. The

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

3. reverse position applies to a man. It is immaterial whether the relationship is of the whole blood or half blood. However, where the circumstances are beyond their control and they want to marry, they can seek the permission of the judge of a High Court to so marry and the marriage become legal.
4. **Neither Party must be already Married**
Since monogamous marriage implies to a marriage to one woman at the exclusion of others, it is a criminal offence for a man to marry another woman while the first marriage subsist. A man may contract a marriage under the Act with the wife he contracted under the customary law marriage but not to another woman.
5. **Consent of the Parties**
It is a concluded precedent that both parties to the marriage must consent to the marriage. Any consent by fraud or duress nullifies the marriage.
6. **Sanity**
Both parties must be sane and should understand the marriage they are contracting or else the marriage will be void ab initio.

The Role of the Registrar

There are preliminary procedures to be followed before the marriage is regarded as legal. The registrar must give a form to be filled by the intended couple which will serve as notice of marriage. The form is filled into marriage Notice Book. After 21 days and up to 3 months from the day of filing the notice, the registrar will issue a certificate to enable the couple get married where there is no caveat entered against the marriage.

The certificate together with the sworn affidavit is given to the priest who will perform the marriage ceremony. It should be noted that under special case, a Governor of a state can grant permission to the couple to avoid the period of the notice and the issuance of the registrar's certificate. Where a caveat is entered, it must be dispersed with by the High Court Judge within the shortest possible time by calling the couple and the person who made the caveat to iron out the issues involved.

Celebration in a Licensed Place of Worship

The celebration of marriage must take place in a license place of worship or in the Registrar's office to be witnessed by at least two persons between 10am to 4pm. Any marriage can be celebrated outside a church or the Registrar's office on special permission. However, the celebration must be carried out by the registrar or minister of Religion. A minister of religion is enjoined not to celebrate any marriage if he knows of any just impediment to such marriage. Further, it is mandatory that he should not solemnize a marriage until the parties thereto deliver to him the registrar's certificate or a special license.

There have been a number of contested cases in Nigeria Courts as to whether marriages contracted in church without a Registrar's license are null and void. In **Obiekwe V. Obiekwe** a marriage solemnize in the Holy Ghost Roman Catholic Church, Enugu was not declared null and void because the court found that the couple did not knowingly and willfully acquiesce in the marriage without the requisite license.

However, the judge in the course of the judgment made the following remark "A good deed has been said about "church marriage" or marriage under Roman Catholic church law", so far as the law of Nigeria is concerned, there is only one form of monogamous marriage, and that is marriage under the ordinance. Legally a marriage in a church

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

(of any denomination), is either a marriage under the ordinance or it is nothing” The Court also had a word for the priest who conducted this marriage. He said “the fault is entirely that of the officiating priest who on his own admission made no attempt whether to explain to the parties this legal position or even ask them whether they wanted to be married under the ordinance or not. His attitude seems to be that he knows very little about the marriage ordinance and is not interested. As the law of Nigeria confers upon priests and ministers of religion, the right to officiate at marriages recognized by the state, it is their duty to make themselves familiar with the ordinance and to see that people who come to them to be married understand their legal position”.

Some religious denomination performs what we call “church blessing of marriage”. These churches insist that if their members marry under customary law or under the statute by appearing before the Registrar of marriages, the marriage will only be recognized by the church either by another church marriage or church blessing of the marriage. Church Blessing of marriage does not constitute a marriage under Nigeria law nor does it add anything to an existing recognize marriage. In **Martins V Adenugba** where a priest blessed a customary law marriage; he issued a certificate to the parties in respect of the ceremony. It was later contended that there was a valid marriage under the marriage Act. The Court held that the ceremony was merely the blessing of a customary law marriage and therefore did not constitute a marriage under the statute.

What Are Rights and Obligations?

Statutory law marriage like its customary counterpart confers on couples therein certain rights and obligations that are peculiar to those who have acquired that status in life. -But before examining these rights, it is instructive to look at what rights and obligations connote.

Right taken in the abstract sense means justice, ethical correctness or consonance with the rule of law. It could also mean power, privilege, interest in one person and incident upon another or power of free action.

But leaving the abstract sense and giving it a juristic content, “right” is one man’s capacity to influence the act of another by means not of his own strength but of the force of organized society.

On the other hand, obligation has been defined as a duty, the bond of legal necessity, which binds together two or more individuals. It is limited to legal duties arising out of a special personal relationship between them, whether by reason of a contract or tort or otherwise.

Rights and Obligation of Parties under Statutory Law Marriage

The Courts have highlighted a number of rights and duties which spouses owe to each other in their domestic life. In *Re-fry* it was held that one marriage a wife has a right to use her husband’s surname. And in **Fendel V Goldsmith**, it was decided that a wife has a right to retain her husband’s surname even after the marriage has been brought to an end either by divorce or death of the husband.

Again in **Cowley V Cowley**, it was held that husband has no right to stop his divorced wife by injunction from using his name unless she is doing so for the purpose of defrauding him and other.

The followings are some of the rights and obligations of parties to a statutory marriage:

1. **Consortium:** This is an embracing term used to denote the association between a husband and wife whereby each is entitled to companionship, love, affection, comfort and support of the other. Consortium is used to explain the bundle of rights which each spouse enjoys by virtue of marriage. For example it is generally accepted that the husband is the breadwinner of the home; although, this position may vary depending on the circumstance.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Another attribute or incident of consortium is the right of the spouses to cohabit. On marriage, the wife and husband has a right to insist on living together physically under the same roof. However, this is not absolute, being subject to the circumstances of the parties, where for instance the nature of the job so demands, the spouses may live apart for most of the time but this must be done by mutual consent of the parties. In **R.V. Creamer** the husband could not cohabit with the wife because he was on military service abroad.

It should however be noted that the spouses have a right of action against each other for deliberate withdrawal from cohabitation which constitute a matrimonial offence of desertion as was held in the case of **Pulford V Pulford**.

Another attribute of consortium is the right of the spouses to consummate the marriage. The parties to a marriage owe each other a right to sexual intercourse. Incapacity to consummate the marriage which may arise from impotence of one spouse may constitute a ground for nullity of marriage as provided for in Section 5 (1) (A) of the Matrimonial Causes Act. However, the right to sexual intercourse with each other must be exercised reasonably and with due regard to the health and disposition of each other. Consequently, while there is right to have sexual relation, a spouse is not bound to submit to excessive sexual demands of the party which will be detrimental to his or her health.

As part of the right to be enjoyed by the parties to the marriage, the law confers on a spouse the right to use such as is necessary in aiding or defending the other spouse who is assaulted or who is under reasonable apprehension of death. By virtue of Section 32(3) of the Criminal Code, a spouse may use force if necessary in order to resist activities or unlawful violence threatened to the other spouse in his presence.

Also any of the spouse to a statutory marriage has a right of action against any third party who wrongfully and unlawfully entices or procures or induces a spouse to violate the duties owed each other.

2. Husband Liability on Wife's Contract: Another right which accrues to parties to a statutory marriage, particularly the wife is the right to make her husband liable for contract entered into. Generally, the fact of marriage, in itself does not authorize a wife to bind the husband in contract. However, if the wife cohabits with her husband and manages his household, there is a presumption of the fact that she is his agent, and has authority to pledge his credit in all domestic matters which are ordinarily entrusted to a wife. However, the wife's authority to pledge her husband's credit is limited to the purchase of necessaries to wit: food, clothing medicine, lodging and those goods and services which are suitable and sufficient in quantity and necessary in fact according to the position in life of the husband.

This right of the wife to pledge her husband's credit is subject to sufficient means of support. Thus were the wife is already sufficiently provided for, or where she has her own means of support, she is not entitled to pledge her husband's credit.

3. Husband and Wife in the Law of Tort: Another obligation which parties to a statutory law marriage have is that no husband or wife shall be entitled to sue each other for a tort except where such other for a tort except where such action is taken by the wife for the purpose of protecting her private property. However, where a husband commits a tort against his wife in the capacity of an agent of a third party, the wife can recover against her husband's principal. This was the position in the case of **Smith V Moss**. With regard to third parties, the combined effect of section 1 (2) and section 12 of the Act is to enable third parties to sue a married woman in respect of both nuptial and post nuptial torts. Her husband also becomes liable to third parties for the torts of his wife. The married women's property Act under section 12 confers on married women, the right to institute civil proceedings against all persons including their husbands and for the protection and security of their own properties. This is a clear exception to the general rule prohibiting tortious action between, husband and wife. This position was followed by the court in **Edet V Edet** in that case it was held that a woman has power to institute an action in tort against her husband,

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

4. Ajabor and Chukwuma: Continental J. Arts and Humanities 7 (1): 40 - 47, 2015

primarily for the protection of her private property.

5. **Right to Bring Action on Death of a Spouse:** This is another right which accrues to the spouses of a statutory marriage, particularly the husband's right to bring action against any third party, whose wrongful act causes the death of the wife 26. It provides that action can be brought for the benefit of the immediate family of the deceased, which include the parents, children or wife of the deceased. This statutory provision was applied in **Jirogho V Anamali** where the executors of the deceased woman were allowed to bring a civil action against the person who caused the death of the deceased.

6. **Husband and Wife in the Law of Evidence:** Special consideration is given to the relationship between husband and wife of a statutory marriage by the provisions of the Law of evidence. For example, in all civil proceeding, the wife or husband is a competent witness and he or she can testify for or against the other spouse. The law makes it clear in spite of the relationship of marriage which makes it possible for each to be competent witnesses. Section 160 (28) of the Evidence Act creates instances where the husband or wife of a person charged with any offence is a competent and compellable witness only on the application of the person charged.

In addition to the above, the Evidence Act and Criminal Code confer special defenses only on husband and wives of statutory marriage. For example in a criminal charge, a wife may plead as a defense that she was compelled by her husband to commit the wrongful act in his presence. This defense of course is not available to the wife of a customary law marriage.

7. **Husband and Wife in Criminal Law:** Criminal law provides for criminal liability of husband wife. the Criminal Code provides that a wife is not criminally responsible for any act which she is actually compelled to do by her husband in his presence, provided that such an act is not an offence punishable by death or is one in which grievous bodily harm is an element. Again, Section 10 of the same code confers a right on the wife of a statutory marriage by not making her an accessory by helping her husband to escape punishment.

Also a husband cannot be guilty of any offence of unlawful carnal knowledge of his wife. Parties to the statutory marriage in Nigeria also enjoy other rights like right to bring action against the spouse for such ancillary reliefs as order for maintenance in favour of a spouse or children of the marriage and actions for custody of children of the marriage. Again statutory marriage empowers the spouses to sue for other matrimonial causes like restoration of conjugal rights, judicial separation, divorce etc.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Parties to the statutory marriage are conferred with plethora of rights and obligations. While these rights are necessary for the survival of marriage institution, it is respectfully submitted that some of them needs a total review to reflect the needs of our contemporary society.

One would wonder why a woman of a failed marriage should be allowed to continue to bear the surname of her formal husband with the man having no power to stop same except where such name is being used fraudulently by the woman. The writers humbly recommend that once a marriage is dissolved, parties to it should return to their formal status. Also the right to pledge credit is only that of the wife, the husband has no such right.

Furthermore, the wife also has the sole right to sue the husband in tort for her properties where the marriage fails. It is believed that these positions of the law were taken at the time when the husband was the sole breadwinner of the house and in control of the home. But times have changed, situations abound in a depressed economy like ours where the breadwinner of the home is the wife and sometimes threatens to throw the unemployed husband out of their matrimonial home which she is the rent payer. The question is what happens to the poor man's property where he is driven to the street by the Iron-lady of the home.

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

It is submitted that these aspect of the law should also be made to apply to the husband of a statutory marriage- what is good for the goose is also good for the gender.

It is hoped that if these areas of the weakness of the law is reviewed, it will help in curbing some matrimonial recklessness of parties to a statutory marriage.

REFERENCES

Nwogugu E.I family Law in Nigeria: Heinemann Educational Books, Nigeria Black Law Dictionary 8th Edition (USA West Publishing Co. 2004)

Osborn Concise Law Dictionary 9th Edition (London: Sweet and Maxwell 2001)

Cases Cited

Corbett V Corbett (1970) 2 WLR 1308

Cowley V Cowley (1901) AC 450

Edet V Edet (1966) ENLR 90

Fendel V Goldsmith (1977) 2 P.D 263

Hyde V Hyde (1886) L.R.I .P. & D 130

Jirogho V Anamali (1958) WRNLR 195

Martins V Adenugba (1946) NLR 63

Obiekwe v Obiebwe (1963) ENLR 196

Okpanum V Okpanum (1972) 2ECCLR 561

Omoga V Badejo (1985) NCNLR 1075

Osanwoyi V Osanwoyi (1975) NMLR 26

Pulford V Pulford (1923) T.L.R 35

R V Creamer (1919) I.K.B.564 Re-Fry (1945) CH 348

Smith V Moss (1940) I.K.B 424

Statutes

Child Right Act cap M7 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004,

Criminal Code cap 77 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

Evidence Act Cap El 4 Laws of the Federation 2004.

Fatal Accident Act 1846

Married Women Property Act 1882

Matrimonial Causes Act Cap m7 Law of the Federation 2004

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)